

Journal of Ubiquitous Music: A multidisciplinary feature-targeted, research-oriented publication

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Abstract. *We present a proposal for a new publication, oriented exclusively to the advancement of knowledge on ubiquitous music practices and research. The objective of our talk is to share the initial ideas and to gather suggestions and opinions on this project from our community at large. The proposed publication will be hosted by the Arts Graduate Program of the Federal University of Espírito Santo. The selection process is linked to the Ubiquitous Music Workshops. A broadly targeted submission will be chosen as the featured article. This piece will be complemented with a series of invited or spontaneous commentaries. This blog-like format constitutes a volume. The target is a golden-access format, well-indexed and aligned with the requirements of Scielo or similar open-science repositories. We aim for a multilingual journal with a single language per volume and a summary of the highlights translated to English. Another proposal involves the incorporation of alternative presentation formats, reflecting not only the advances in the contents of ubimus research, but also impacting the methods for delivery and presentation.*

References

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